

Toxicity Studies on *Sorghum Bicolor* Infusion Mixed with Different Additives on Selected Organs in Weanling Rats

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Abstract

Herbal infusions are sources of biologically active compounds responsible for managing varying conditions. This study investigated the toxicological implications of *Sorghum bicolor* (SB) infusion, both plain and combined with various dietary additives, on selected organs of weanling rats. Weanling rats were divided into nine experimental groups: a positive control group administered distilled water and eight treatment groups placed on SB sheath infused at 100 °C for 10 minutes, either plain or supplemented with ginger, lemongrass, alligator pepper, garlic, milk, sugar, or honey at ratio 4:1. Following a 28-day administration period, organ-to-body weight ratios (liver, kidney, stomach), serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) levels, and histopathological profiles were assessed. The treatment groups exhibited significantly elevated liver and kidney weight ratios ranging between 37.6% to 65.3% and 25.6% to 66.7%, respectively, compared to the control, indicating organ hypertrophy. The SB plain group exhibited comparatively lower GGT activity, while the control, ginger, milk, and honey groups demonstrated higher GGT levels. Despite these findings, histological examination revealed no significant pathological changes in liver, kidney, or stomach tissues across all groups. Conclusively, *Sorghum bicolor* sheath infusion, whether administered alone or with selected additives, elicited modest physiological alterations in organ indices but no histopathological damage, indicating general safety under short-term use. These findings support its potential functional use as a nutraceutical.

Keywords: *Sorghum bicolor*, infusion, histopathology, additives, GGT

INTRODUCTION

One of the main cereal crops in many regions of Asia and Africa is *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench, it has garnered increasing attention not only for its nutritional benefits but also for its traditional medicinal uses. Traditionally consumed as food and herbal infusion, phenolic

acids, flavonoids, and anthocyanins are among the many bioactive phytochemicals found in *S. bicolor* that have been implicated in antioxidative, anti-anaemic, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial qualities (Birhanu, 2021; Oladiji et al., 2007; Subbarayan et al., 2022). These attributes have led to its inclusion in traditional medicine for managing conditions such as anaemia, inflammation, and diabetes (Khalid et al., 2022). Phytochemicals have been implicated in the healing of various health disorders, therefore acting as sources of new drug research and development (Gonfa et al., 2023). Herbal infusions have been argued to be user-friendly herbal formulations that are prescribed for patients to provide a better distribution of bioactive compounds in the intestine (Studzińska-Sroka et al., 2021).

Despite these purported health benefits, the safety of *S. bicolor* preparations, especially when combined with various additives, has not been extensively characterized. Additives, whether natural (e.g., honey, ginger, lemon) or synthetic (e.g., sweeteners, preservatives), are incorporated into traditional infusions to enhance flavour, therapeutic potential, or shelf life (Enejo & Martins, 2024). However, such modifications may alter the pharmacokinetic and toxicological profiles of the constituent compounds, leading to potential organ-specific toxicities.

Weanling rats are frequently utilized in toxicity studies due to their heightened sensitivity to xenobiotics, their rapid metabolic development, and their relevance as models for juvenile human physiology (Olson et al., 2000). About 80% of the population worldwide, especially in developing countries, is dependent on herbal medicines (Fiadjoe & Koffuor, 2024) hence the need to ascertain the safety of these formulations. Understanding the effects of *S. bicolor* infusion with various additives, based on its pharmacological claims on critical organs such as the liver, kidneys, and stomach, is pivotal for establishing its safety, particularly in vulnerable populations.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to assess the subacute toxicity of *Sorghum bicolor* infusion with various additives in weanling rats. By assessing histopathological and biochemical changes in selected organs, the study aims to provide evidence-based insights into the safety and potential risks posed by such herbal formulations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

The voucher number UILH/001/1043 was given to the *Sorghum bicolor* sheath at the University of Ilorin, Nigeria's Plant Biology Department, after it was acquired from Ilora, Oyo State. The sheath was dried and pulverized, after which it was mixed with spices (ginger, garlic, alligator pepper, lemon grass) at the ratio 4:1. The groups with honey, milk, and sugar were added at the point of administration to the experimental animals.

Enzyme Assay Kit

The Gamma Glutamyl Transferase (GGT) kit used was a product of Fortress Diagnostics Limited, United Kingdom.

Principle

The substrate L- γ -glutamyl-3-carboxy-4-nitroanilide, in the presence of glycylglycine, is converted to 5-amino-2-nitrobenzoate by γ -glutamyl transferase, measured at 405 nm. The increase in absorbance is proportional to γ -glutamyl transferase activity.

Histological Study

The method described by Manzoor et al. (2021) was used.

Laboratory Animals

For this investigation, 45 rats weighing an average of 40.00 ± 10.00 g were acquired from the Central Research Laboratories' Animal Holding Unit at the University of Ilorin in Nigeria. The ethical committee granted consent for this investigation under approval number UERC/ASN/2015/215. For 28 days, the rats were divided into nine groups of five, and each group received 1600 mg/kg body weight of *Sorghum bicolor* sheath infusion.

Statistical Analysis

GraphPad Prism 6 and SPSS package version 21 were utilized. The mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM) was used to express the values. To ascertain statistical significance, the values were put through Duncan's multiple range test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). At $p < 0.05$, differences were deemed significant.

Results

Figure 1: Serum Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase (GGT) concentration of rats orally administered *Sorghum bicolor* infusion with selected additives at 1600 mg/kg body weight for 28 days

The values are the means of five calculations \pm SEM. CONTROL: Positive Control Rats; SBPL: *Sorghum bicolor* + plain; SBGN: *Sorghum bicolor* + ginger, SBLG: *Sorghum bicolor* + lemongrass; SBAL: *Sorghum bicolor* + alligator pepper; SBGA: *Sorghum bicolor* + garlic; SBML: *Sorghum bicolor* + milk; SBSU: *Sorghum bicolor* + sugar; SBHN: *Sorghum bicolor* + honey

Table 1: Percentage organ-to-bodyweight ratio of rats after orally receiving *Sorghum bicolor* infusion with selected additives for 28 days

Groups	Liver	Kidney	Stomach
Control	3.75 ± 0.19^a	0.78 ± 0.03^a	0.81 ± 0.03^a
SB plain	5.16 ± 0.31^b	0.98 ± 0.05^b	1.03 ± 0.05^a
SB ginger	6.20 ± 0.16^b	1.30 ± 0.16^c	0.93 ± 0.10^a
SB lemon grass	6.16 ± 0.22^b	1.13 ± 0.05^{bc}	0.97 ± 0.06^a
SB alligator pepper	6.12 ± 0.21^b	1.15 ± 0.07^{bc}	1.04 ± 0.18^a
SB garlic	5.95 ± 0.95^b	1.17 ± 0.04^{bc}	0.93 ± 0.07^a
SB milk	5.42 ± 0.01^b	0.98 ± 0.01^{ab}	0.84 ± 0.01^a
SB sugar	5.94 ± 0.20^b	1.06 ± 0.03^b	1.48 ± 0.28^b
SB honey	5.88 ± 0.01^b	1.06 ± 0.01^b	0.83 ± 0.01^a

The values are the means of five calculations \pm SEM. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by values varying in superscripts down the column. SB: *Sorghum bicolor*

Plate 1: Rat liver cross-section after oral infusion of *Sorghum bicolor* with selected additives for 28 days (mg x100)

A- Control, B- Plain SB, C- SB + Ginger, D- SB + Lemon Grass, E- SB + Alligator Pepper, F- SB + Garlic, G- SB + Milk, H- SB + Sugar, I- SB + Honey. Plate 1 shows hepatic tissues with preserved architecture, comprising hepatocytes, portal tracts, and central veins, in the liver of all groups except those treated with *S. bicolor* with lemon grass-, and alligator pepper, which showed moderate portal and lobular inflammation (blue arrow). Other groups had mild portal lymphocytic infiltration (black arrow).

Plate 2: Rat kidney cross-section after oral infusion of *Sorghum bicolor* with selected additives for 28 days (mg x100)

A- Control, B- Plain SB, C- SB + Ginger, D- SB + Lemon Grass, E- SB + Alligator Pepper, F- SB + Garlic, G- SB + Milk, H- SB + Sugar, I- SB + Honey. Renal tissues with preserved architecture comprising glomeruli (black arrow), tubules (red arrow), and blood vessels were observed.

Plate 3: Rat stomach cross-section after oral infusion of *Sorghum bicolor* with selected additives for 28 days (mg x100)

A- Control, B- Plain SB, C- SB + Ginger, D- SB + Lemon Grass, E- SB + Alligator Pepper, F- SB + Garlic, G- SB + Milk, H- SB + Sugar, I- SB + Honey. There were mild infiltrations

by the neutrophils at the basal layer (black arrow) in all the groups, however, there was no atrophy or metaplastic changes.

DISCUSSION

Medicinal infusions have, over time, gained more popularity, especially among the low-income population, due to their availability, affordability, and belief that they cause minimal to no side effects (Awenede et al., 2023). The liver can detoxify toxic substances and synthesize useful metabolites (Meyer *et al.*, 2001; Arun *et al.*, 2014), and cholestatic-inducing enzymes such as gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) are reported to have originated from it (Ayembilla et al., 2023). GGT catalyses the transfer of the gamma-glutamyl moiety of glutathione to an amino acid, peptide, or water to form glutamate (Arun *et al.*, 2014). Rats' serum GGT levels were significantly lower after receiving plain *Sorghum bicolor*, lemon grass, alligator pepper, and garlic for 28 days than the control group (Figure 1). It has been reported that plants that can reduce the serum GGT levels when compared to controls have hepatoprotective effects (Saenthaweesuk et al., 2017). The significant reduction observed in the groups treated with garlic, lemon grass, and alligator pepper may be due to the hepatoprotective abilities reported for these spices (Alharbi et al., 2024; Almatroodi et al., 2020; Idoko & Imam, 2024). It should, however, be noted that reduced activity observed in infusions with spices as well as the plain SB could be due to synergistic actions among the metabolites present in the spices and the plant, hence leading to reduced activity. The hepatoprotective effect observed in this study is in agreement with previous studies that *Sorghum bicolor* has hepatoprotective effects (Ademiluyi et al., 2014; Ajiboye et al., 2024; Akande et al., 2010; Oladiji et al., 2007).

The organ body weight ratio is a marker of toxicity for specific organs, as a deleterious drug effect can be identified using this marker (Ayembilla et al., 2023; Donkor et al., 2014). It is a marker for any underlying pathological condition; it could be an increase or a shrinkage in the organ compared to the control. The significant increase (organomegaly) observed in the organ-body weight ratio of the liver of all the groups (Table 1), except for the control group, may be due to hypertrophy of the liver and kidneys. The 1600 mg/kg body weight dosage administered to the rats may have induced swelling of the organs; therefore, the use of lower doses as nutraceuticals is advised. This finding is in support of that reported by Ajiboye et al. on *Sorghum bicolor* sheath, who reported hypertrophy at 2000 mg/kg body weight (Ajiboye et al., 2024). This deleterious effect was, however, not observed in the stomach, as there was no significant difference in almost all the groups except for those with sugar. Intake of processed sugars has been linked to disruption of the intestinal barrier, leading to increased gut permeability and ultimately enhancing susceptibility to infection (Arnone et al., 2022). This could have been responsible for the swelling observed in the stomach of the group administered SB with sugar; however, for the other groups, the report is in agreement with the report of Ezejiofor et al., as reported for *C. afer ker Gawl* (Ezejiofor et al., 2013).

Organ-to-body weight ratios cannot be directly extrapolated to humans, as they vary with multiple factors, including race, gender, age, environmental conditions, and socio-economic status (Vaibhav et al., 2022). Consequently, no universal standard value exists, underscoring the need to rely on complementary assays for accurate interpretation.

The histological examination carried out on the liver showed preserved architecture for all the groups, except for the groups treated with lemon grass and alligator pepper, which had mild inflammation. This is suggestive of hepatotoxicity, most likely due to the high dosage used. There was also no significant distortion in the renal tissues as intact glomeruli, tubules, and blood vessels were seen, and there were no degenerative changes. The stomach tissues had no sign of atrophy across the groups (Plates 1-3), and this shows that *Sorghum bicolor* infusion with additives may be safe, but at a reduced concentration.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study demonstrates the hepatoprotective potential of plain *Sorghum bicolor* and its infusions with garlic, lemongrass, and alligator pepper, as evidenced by the significant reduction in serum GGT levels. However, the observed liver hypertrophy and mild inflammation at 1600 mg/kg bodyweight highlight the need for caution in dosage, supporting the use of lower concentrations when applied as nutraceuticals. Overall, while the infusions appear safe for the stomach and kidneys, their hepatotoxic potential at high doses warrants further investigation.

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